

ATRIUM – Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities

Work Package WP1
Coordination and Project Management

Deliverable D1.3
ATRIUM Policy Brief

Funding Instrument: Horizon Europe
Call: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01
Call Topic: Research infrastructure services to support health research, accelerate the green and digital transformation, and advance frontier knowledge (2023)
Project Start: 1 Jan 2024
Project Duration: 48 months
Project Coordinator: DARIAH
Document Identifier: 10.5281/zenodo.17788168

**Funded by
the European Union**

Deliverable Information

Action Number:	101132163
Action Acronym:	ATRIUM
Action title:	Advancing FronTier Research In the Arts and hUManities
Deliverable Number:	D1.3
Deliverable Full Title:	ATRIUM Policy Brief
Document Identifier:	D1.3-ATRIUM-Policy-Brief-25-12-31
Beneficiary in Charge:	DARIAH
Report Version:	v1.0
Contractual Date:	31/12/2025
Report Submission Date:	09/12/2025
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Report
Lead Author(s):	Toma Tasovac, Anne Baillot, Megan Black
Reviewers:	Guntram Geser, Julian Richards
Keywords:	research infrastructures, research evaluation, workflows, arts and humanities, digital humanities, policy recommendations
Status:	Final

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List of Abbreviations

A&H	Arts and Humanities
ATRIUM	Advancing Transnational Research Infrastructures in the Arts and Humanities
ARIADNE	ARIADNE Research Infrastructure AISBL
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
DG	Directorate-General
DG CNECT	Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
DG EAC	Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DORA	San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment
EASSH	European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FP10	10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (Horizon Europe 2028–2034)
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums

HTR	Handwritten Text Recognition
IP	Intellectual Property
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
PID	Persistent Identifier
RI	Research Infrastructure
SF-DORA	San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
TNA	Transnational Access

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes made
05/09/25	v0.1	Megan Black	Draft report template and research
13/10/25	v0.2	Toma Tasovac	Draft chapter outlines
07/11/25	v0.3	Megan Black	Draft chapter on policy landscape
08/11/25	v0.4	Anne Baillot	Draft chapter on the ATRIUM project
13/11/25	v0.5	Toma Tasovac	Revise chapters 2 and 3; draft introduction and policy recommendations
25/11/25	v0.6	Gunter Geser, Julian Richards	External Review
09/12/25	v1.0	Megan Black	Submission

Executive Summary

ATRIUM brings together 30 partners from 12 countries, including four major European research infrastructures (RIs) – DARIAH, ARIADNE, CLARIN, and OPERAS – to strengthen the foundations of arts and humanities (A&H) research across Europe. The project tackles long-standing structural barriers in the RI landscape: fragmented access to resources, uneven interoperability, reproducibility gaps, undervaluation of non-traditional research outputs, and persistent inequalities across regions and languages.

Funded by the European Commission, ATRIUM addresses these challenges through an integrated service and software catalogue, a catalogue of reusable workflows, an assessment framework for non-traditional research outputs aligned with the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), and a transnational access (TNA) programme that expands skills and participation.

To ensure that Europe can maintain an open, diverse and globally competitive A&H research ecosystem, this Policy Brief, aimed at European Union (EU) and national policymakers, research funders and research infrastructure leaders, proposes the following policy recommendations:

1. **Reaffirm the foundational nature of curiosity-driven research.** Embed a clear, programmatic statement in Horizon Europe 2028-34 and national RI strategies that fundamental, curiosity-driven A&H research is indispensable for a resilient, self-reflective and culturally diverse Europe.
2. **Make workflows first-class research outputs.** Require funded projects creating or using workflows to publish them FAIRly with PIDs, versioning and environment capture (e.g., containers), and to deposit them in discoverable registries (e.g., SSH Open Marketplace). Recognise workflows and workflow papers in evaluations, aligned with CoARA/DORA.
3. **Adopt the 2024 Revised Charter for Access to RIs across A&H.** Update institutional access policies to align with the Revised European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures (2024), ensuring transparent, equitable access; clear cost models; continuity in crises; and proportionate research security by design.
4. **Scale TNA and mobility to close widening gaps.** Increase TNA funding for under-resourced languages/regions, continue to provide remote/hybrid options, and explicitly align TNA schemes with the ERA structural policies on attractive

research careers and cross-border mobility. Where appropriate, explore synergies with Erasmus+ mobility actions (e.g., staff training, doctoral mobility) so that visits to RI TNA hosts can be recognised or co-funded through established EU mobility pathways.

5. **Institutionalise fairer research assessment and open peer review.** Promote CoARA-aligned policies that recognise diverse research outputs (datasets, software, workflows, training); prioritise qualitative, expert judgement with responsible metrics; and support open peer-review models that accommodate such outputs.
6. **Consolidate human capacity for open, sustainable A&H research.** Invest in long-term roles (data stewards, workflow engineers, community curators), shared curricula (e.g. via DARIAH-Campus), and ATRIUM-style cross-RI training measures aligned to EOSC and data-space needs. Complement these with formalised career frameworks that describe role profiles, progression pathways and evaluation criteria that credit infrastructure work.
7. **Mandate common data-sharing policies and rights clarity across Member States.** Promote national adoption of interoperable, EOSC-compatible policies (PIDs, machine-readable licences, and data rights management, including consent and ethics for sensitive data) so that Open Science ambitions translate into day-to-day, cross-border practices.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This brief provides targeted advice on how the ATRIUM project informs European, national and institutional policy for research infrastructures (RIs) serving the arts and humanities (A&H). It focuses on four persistent barriers: fragmented access, reproducibility, recognition of non-traditional research outputs and inequalities in access and skills, and outlines how ATRIUM addresses them through a consolidated service portfolio, reusable workflows, fairer assessment practices and transnational access.

The intended audiences are the European Commission, particularly the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) and Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CNECT), European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) bodies, national research ministries and funders, RI managers, and CoARA signatories.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Chapter 2 summarizes the policy landscape (Revised Access Charter 2024; European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2025-27; Horizon Europe orientations 2028-2034; ESFRI directions; and EOSC). Chapter 3 presents ATRIUM's diagnosis of A&H challenges (3.1) and what the project delivers (3.2). Section 4 sets out seven concrete, actionable policy recommendations.

2. Policy Landscape

This chapter provides a brief overview of the policy landscape for research infrastructures in Europe. Recurring themes throughout are the importance of Open Science and better access to research through the interoperability of data and services, long-term data stewardship and the reform of research assessment.

2.1 Revised European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures (2024)

Building on the 2015 European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures (European Commission 2015), the revised version reinforces the need for open and equitable access to services, metadata and results of publicly funded research across all research domains (European Commission 2024). A notable addition is the necessity of the continuity of access to RIs in times of crisis, such as pandemics or geopolitical disruptions, and calls for mechanisms that protect researchers and infrastructures from interruptions. Moreover, the 2024 Charter highlights the growing diversity of RI users, including small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and cross-sectoral actors, and the importance of designing access policies that are responsive to their needs.

2.2 European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2025-2027

As with the first ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024 (European Commission 2022), the Council Recommendation on the ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027 (Council of the European Union 2025) outlines a strategic framework and three-year roadmap that directly affects the evolution of research infrastructures and the broader research ecosystem. Addressing systemic barriers and the challenges of artificial intelligence and research security, the latest agenda prioritises Open Science, EOSC, long-term data stewardship, and the reform of research assessment.

The ERA agenda calls for coordinated support for persistent identifiers, data rights management, and shared access policies to ensure the reusability and transparency of research outputs. It also promotes a reform of research assessment practices under CoARA. These shifts are critical to enabling more inclusive and sustainable research careers, facilitating mobility, and improving access to high-quality research across Europe.

2.3 Horizon Europe 2028-2034

The European Commission's proposal for the next Framework Programme, Horizon Europe 2028–2034 (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation 2025; European Commission 2025), positions research and technology infrastructures as core enablers of scientific excellence, innovation, and strategic autonomy. While still under consultation, the draft orientations indicate a significantly expanded budget for RIs and a focus on “moonshot” priorities such as artificial intelligence, data technologies, and green transitions. These ambitions are coupled with commitments to research security and the principle of “security-by-design”.

However, several stakeholders have raised concerns about the balance of priorities within the new programme. The European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities (EASSH) argues that Europe's long-term progress depends not only on technological innovation but equally on addressing the social challenges that shape citizens' wellbeing and the sustainability of European democracies (2025). EASSH calls for all clusters of Horizon Europe to be more equally resourced, ensuring that social, cultural, and ethical research questions receive comparable attention to technical ones. Without such balance, Europe risks overlooking the societal understanding necessary to deliver inclusive and effective innovation.

2.4 ESFRI Directions

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) provides the strategic compass for developing a coherent and sustainable European RI landscape. Its most recent directions underline the need to strengthen the sustainability, accessibility, and resilience of research infrastructures through enhanced cooperation and better alignment of European, national, and regional priorities. ESFRI emphasises the long-term viability and interoperability of infrastructures, advocating for a roadmap that enables interconnection and integration across disciplines (ESFRI 2017; 2018). A major focus of ESFRI is the transition toward a truly interoperable data ecosystem embedded within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

2.5 European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

[EOSC](#) remains the central policy vehicle for implementing Open Science principles in Europe. It aims to provide a federated environment where researchers can publish, find, and reuse data, tools, and services across disciplines. The EOSC policy framework stresses the importance of long-term data stewardship, persistent identifiers, data rights, and transparent access policies to ensure the reusability and reproducibility of scientific knowledge.

3. ATRIUM Project

The ATRIUM project was conceived to foster synergies between 30 partners across 12 countries, including four research infrastructures (DARIAH, ARIADNE, CLARIN and OPERAS). Its goal is also to operationalise EOSC and ERA principles for the A&H in direct response to researchers' needs. ATRIUM combines ongoing analysis of challenges, needs and risks with the development of open, interoperable services and reusable workflows across infrastructures.

3.1 Challenges for A&H Research Infrastructures

Arts and humanities research infrastructures face a range of challenges. Four key challenges are tackled jointly in the context of the ATRIUM project.

A first impediment concerns the conditions of access to information relevant to A&H research. In practice, access is fragmented, with insufficient connections across domains, languages and media. A historian studying 20th-century migration may need to navigate separate catalogues for digitised newspapers, ship passenger lists and border-control records, census and population statistics, maps, and oral history collections, each using different metadata schemas and vocabularies. While standards exist within specific communities, there is no shared layer for cross-RI semantic interoperability, which severely limits the discoverability and combination of resources across infrastructures.

Second, arts and humanities are often wrongly considered to be less affected by the current reproducibility crisis that is impacting research in other fields, e.g. natural sciences. Yet they too rely on data and methods that need to be made accessible for reproduction purposes. Data pipelines used by ATRIUM communities range from Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) followed by manual correction and linguistic annotation, to 3D scanning workflows that combine capture, mesh processing and long-term preservation. In most projects, these pipelines are implemented as ad hoc scripts, local configurations and undocumented sequences of tools. When such projects end, their workflows are rarely documented, versioned or assigned a persistent identifier, making it difficult for other researchers to reproduce or adapt them. Institutional incentives to invest time into designing, testing, and disseminating reusable workflows are weak, meaning that efforts rarely translate into reputation gains. For RIs, tailoring support that addresses all aspects of the issue

(lack of recognition of the problem as well as of its solution) has proven to be particularly difficult.

The other side of the coin is the context of scientific ratings based on impact factors. The overwhelming importance attributed to impact factors tends to overshadow the original quality of individual publications and to marginalise non-traditional formats. In practice, a carefully curated corpus, a robust conversion pipeline between two metadata schemas or a sustainable piece of research software may not even qualify as research in promotion or funding decisions. Yet we know that non-traditional research outputs such as datasets, methods, software, workflows or training material are in fact essential to RIs and their users (Tasovac et al. 2023). Turning this into a virtuous circle of research production would require mutual recognition: on the one hand, of researchers' contribution to RIs, and, on the other, of RIs' role in leveraging the importance of these types of research output. The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (SF-DORA) and CoARA have demonstrated that prevailing assessment practices across higher education and the research system at large continue to hinder the healthy development of open, diverse and trustworthy research practices.

Finally, the considerable growth in accessible data and services is only partially contributing to reducing inequalities. Lesser resourced areas and languages continue to face capacity gaps. In many so-called widening countries,¹ and for numerous lesser-used languages, there are still no stable national nodes, certified repositories or locally available training programmes. Researchers depend on ad hoc project hosting, fragile personal networks and short-term funding. How to address this widening inequity gap remains a challenge that requires tackling shortcomings in the available support for skills development as well as travel and access costs.

3.2 What ATRIUM delivers

In the light of this challenging situation, the ATRIUM project is contributing to improve the four above-mentioned target areas.

First, the question of service interoperability is addressed through the joint development of an integrated [Service & Software Catalogue](#). The four participating RIs play a key role in identifying best practices and facilitating the seamless connection of services and resources.

¹ This is defined by the European Commission as less R&I advanced countries for which there is a Horizon Europe Widening Programme.

Second, the project is transformative in conceiving and disseminating reusable workflows in the arts and humanities. ATRIUM supports communities in turning ad hoc pipelines into documented, citable workflows. By ensuring that this collective work is thoroughly documented and connected to European discovery platforms such as the [SSH Open Marketplace](#), ATRIUM contributes to a sustainable ecosystem of open, reusable methods that strengthen the capacity for innovation and collaboration across the social sciences and humanities (SSH).

Thirdly, the lack of recognition of non-traditional research outputs is tackled at its root through the development of concrete assessment criteria that can be implemented in real evaluation contexts. The [ATRIUM Assessment Framework](#) proposes a coherent set of criteria for data papers and training materials, and introduces a new publication category for workflow papers (Gouzi et al. 2025). Work is currently ongoing on evaluation criteria for digital scholarly editions, software and 3D models. A notable additional added value of this contribution, like for the workflows mentioned above, is that it is not purely theoretical: it is tested and refined through concrete use cases. The DARIAH overlay journal *Transformations* is now accepting submissions in the very categories for which the assessment framework was developed, thereby closing the loop between criteria design and actual peer-review practice.

Finally, facilitating networking, disseminating ATRIUM key competences, providing access to resources: these are core benefits of the ATRIUM transnational access program (TNA). With several rounds of application a year, the research grant scheme makes it possible to facilitate travel for a diverse audience of scholars, fostering knowledge exchange and reducing gaps in skills and support. For example, in the first 17 months of the project, [ATRIUM's TNA programme](#) hosted over 133 people from 34 countries. This includes 102 placements at 7 Summer Schools and 31 Individual Access placements at 11 host organisations.

4. Policy Recommendations

The recommendations below build on ATRIUM's analysis of structural challenges in the arts and humanities (A&H) research ecosystem and on the project's concrete experience in developing interoperable services, reusable workflows, fairer assessment practices and equitable transnational access. They are intended to support EU and national policymakers, research funders, research infrastructures and institutions in strengthening the long-term conditions for open, sustainable and curiosity-driven A&H research. Each recommendation addresses a systemic barrier identified in the project and proposes practical measures that can be integrated into Horizon Europe 2028–34, national RI strategies and institutional policies.

4.1 Reaffirm the foundational nature of curiosity-driven research

Action: Embed a clear, programmatic statement in Horizon Europe 2028–34 and national RI strategies that fundamental, curiosity-driven A&H research is indispensable for a resilient, self-reflective and culturally diverse Europe.

Why this matters: Curiosity-driven A&H research sustains Europe's capacity for critical inquiry, democratic resilience, cultural and linguistic diversity, interpretive depth, and long-cycle knowledge. This type of research must be protected from pressures that reduce its value to narrowly defined economic targets, innovation metrics or time-bound "moonshot" objectives. EASSH and others warn against an overly technocratic orientation in discussions on the 10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10). Research infrastructures in ATRIUM are committed to infrastructural work that sustains exploratory research at scale.

Who should implement this? European Commission (EC), such as DG RTD, member states, funders.

4.2 Make workflows first-class research outputs

Action: Require funded projects creating or using workflows to publish them FAIRly with PIDs, versioning and environment capture (e.g., containers), and to deposit them in discoverable registries (e.g., SSH Open Marketplace). Recognise workflows and workflow papers in evaluations, aligned with CoARA/DORA.

Why this matters: Reproducibility and reuse depend on visible, citable processes, and not only on data sets and scholarly articles. Treating workflows as first-class outputs strengthens methodological clarity, reduces duplication of effort, and provides researchers with recognition for labour that is currently invisible. ATRIUM already operationalises this approach across four RIs.

Who should implement this? EC (work programme authors); ESFRI Strategic Working Groups; national funders; RIs; journals and publishers.

4.3 Adopt the 2024 Revised Charter for Access to RIs across A&H

Action: Update institutional access policies to align with the Revised European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures (2024), ensuring transparent, equitable access; clear cost models; continuity in crises; and proportionate research security by design.

Why this matters: The Revised Charter is the EU's agreed reference for modern, equitable and secure access to RIs. A&H infrastructures should benefit from and contribute to the same standards that govern STEM RIs, ensuring coherence, fairness and sustainability across disciplines.

Who should implement this? RI managers; ministries and research councils; national and European funders.

4.4 Scale TNA and mobility to close widening gaps

Action: Increase TNA funding for under-resourced languages/regions, continue to provide remote/hybrid options, and explicitly align TNA schemes with the ERA structural policies on attractive research careers and cross-border mobility. Where appropriate, explore synergies with Erasmus+ mobility actions (e.g., staff training, doctoral mobility) so that visits to RI TNA hosts can be recognised or co-funded through established EU mobility pathways.

Why this matters: RI access is only meaningful when researchers have the financial, administrative and institutional means to travel, collaborate and learn. Mobility gaps deepen inequalities and limit the impact of open services. ATRIUM's TNA scheme showcases a functioning humanities-driven mobility model; linking it to broader EU mobility instruments such as Erasmus+ could generate new synergies, increase participation, and ensure a more equitable distribution of skills and opportunities.

Who should implement this? EC (DG RTD, DG EAC), national research funders, Erasmus+ National Agencies and higher-education international offices, RIs and host institutions.

4.5 Institutionalise fairer research assessment and open peer review

Action: Promote CoARA-aligned policies that recognise diverse research outputs (datasets, software, workflows, training); prioritise qualitative, expert judgement with responsible metrics; and support open peer-review models that accommodate such outputs.

Why this matters: Infrastructural labour remains structurally undervalued, providing little incentive for researchers to invest in sustainable data, software and workflows. Open peer review enhances transparency, accountability and trust, while enabling richer, contextualised assessment of complex, non-traditional outputs. ATRIUM's framework provides ready-to-use criteria that are immediately implementable.

Who should implement this? Universities and research-performing organisations; RI host institutions; research funders; scholarly publishers and journals.

4.6 Consolidate human capacity for open, sustainable A&H research

Action: Invest in long-term roles (data stewards, workflow engineers, community curators), shared curricula (e.g. via DARIAH-Campus), and ATRIUM-style cross-RI training measures aligned to EOSC and data-space needs. Complement these with formalised career frameworks that describe role profiles, progression pathways and evaluation criteria that credit infrastructure work.

Why this matters: The interoperability of research resources and reproducibility of research rely on people and skills, not only platforms. Without stable expertise to curate data, document and maintain workflows, manage PIDs and rights, and support RI user communities, FAIR/EOSC compliance will stall. Moreover, knowledge will continue to be repeatedly lost through staff turnover, deepening inequalities between well-resourced institutions and those without specialist roles. Consolidating human capacity turns one-off project investments into enduring RI capabilities while supporting ERA goals for attractive, sustainable research careers.

Who should implement this? EC; Member States; RIs and repositories; universities as well as Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums (GLAMs).

4.7 Mandate common data-sharing policies and rights clarity across member states

Action: Promote national adoption of interoperable, EOSC-compatible policies (PIDs, machine-readable licences, and data rights management, including consent and ethics for sensitive data) so that Open Science ambitions translate into day-to-day, cross-border practices.

Why this matters: Fragmented national policies and unclear rights regimes create friction and uncertainty in reusing data across borders and sectors. GLAM institutions face complex intellectual property (IP)/privacy decisions, and infrastructure providers struggle to integrate heterogeneous rights information into interoperable discovery systems. Harmonised PID and rights policies reduce legal and administrative burdens, facilitate automation and discovery, and enable researchers to work confidently with cross-border, multilingual A&H data.

Who should implement this? EC & Member States; RIs; repositories; research funders.

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Consortium

Research Infrastructures

Beneficiaries

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